

J. Durga Prasad Rao Additional Director and Academic Dean, HOD Computer Science, Shri Shankaracharya Mahavidyalaya, Junwani, Bhilai, j.durga.prasad.rao@gmail.com
Prachi Sharma Assistant Professor of Education, Pt. Harshankar Shukla College, Raipur, prachihsc95@gmail.com

Abstract

This review article addresses the question of the production of the field relationship between education and technology, from a pedagogical perspective. This is an exploratory exercise based on tracking documentary and categorical of articles published by the Pedagogy and Knowledge magazine, in the period 1990–2017. The analysis proposes that, to understand this field, it is necessary to overcome the limits of the school and the roles traditionally assigned to it. In this sense, some relationships materialized in notions are shown. That exposes the look on the cultural and educational transformations generated by the developments of the technology. The article is organized in three sections that present the conceptual nodes on the relationship education and technology: the pedagogical analysis of the effect of the media in education; the search for inclusion with the use of technology and virtual education; and the subjectivity and experience of interaction in technological environments. As conclusions, the value of critical reflection carried out by researchers in education and technology with the analysis of the effect of the mass media in education, from a perspective pedagogical; the process of incorporating technology for the inclusion of subjects with disabilities and of vulnerable populations and the centrality of the relationship between subjectivity and technology as a cultural environment.

Keywords Media; technical culture; communication; educational technology; computer technology; humanity.

Introduction

In the search for what is produced from the pedagogical perspective, in the field of education and technology, the National Pedagogical University, particularly the Faculty of Education, was found as the setting where pedagogical reflection materializes par excellence in Colombia. . The Pedagogía y Saberes magazine appeared as the space in which pedagogical analysis, questions and criticisms of what happens in the school, the educational system and in society are put on paper.

Education, in the field of education and technology, requires a broader definition, where it is recognized as a symbolic action. According to (Laursen et al., 2021), education is located in areas of daily life in which communication mediates our relationships. Education as a communicative action is, at the same time, an intrasubjective and intersubjective process that occurs in social interaction, which is experienced in technological environments, which have become scenarios of cultural mediation for the construction of systems of meaning. Or interpretative schemes and that, as a whole, configure the symbolic universe of the subjects.

About Pedagogy and Knowledge magazine

The magazine of the Faculty of Education of the National Pedagogical University was selected as a space for documentary tracking, as a scenario in which pedagogical reflections in general and on the relationship between education and technology in particular are recorded. There are publications from 1990, the year in which it was created to make visible and have a space for the dissemination of discussions about education and pedagogy, based on investigative criteria. The Pedagogía y Saberes magazine arose as a result of the searches of researchers and teachers in the eighties and nineties.

The findings are presented in three conceptual nodes that allow us to see the searches and discussions that guided the work of the researchers-authors:

1. The first node brings into play the perspective of researchers who reflect from a critical approach on the effects of technology in education, focused on the notion of the media and the education-

communication relationship, especially in the context contemporary of the end of the last century, when social change and globalization materialized in different areas of life. (Hurajova et al., 2022) in his review on (Zhang et al., 2022), (Ulu-Aslan & Baş, 2023) and (Xu, 2023) identifies the need for change in the school, pedagogical practices and the educational system to assume, from a critical perspective, the challenge of generate strategies that allow continuing training in this context of change and uncertainty.

2. The second node shows the search for the inclusion of people with disabilities and vulnerable populations with the use of technology. (Paris et al., 2021), (Hellin et al., 2023) among others, are authors who work on inclusive processes that link technology. There are also analyzes on virtual education as an alternative to bring education closer to vulnerable populations (Miller, 2021); In this sense, proposals built from the notion of service are analyzed, which gives meaning to the use of technologies in education.

3. The third node indicates the relationship between the field of education and technology as the space where the two practices are interaction scenarios, and in which subjectivity becomes the protagonist of the experience of the subjects in technological environments.

First node: pedagogical criticism of the effect of the media on education

In the first decade of the *Pedagogía y Saberes* magazine, the relationship between education and technology appears in the reflections of the authors in the form of a critique of the entry of the media into the scope of the school and the educational system. This critique points out as a danger the entry of new technologies –mainly television, radio and cinema– in the lives of the subjects, since due to them changes and challenges in pedagogical knowledge and practices would have been generated. The investigations from which the articles published in these early years were derived focused attention on the communicative essence of the technological medium, since it was seen as an artifact without symbolic density. The reflections were organized around both criticism of the media and the education-communication relationship, which functioned as two articulating concepts of the debate in this period. In general, this first conceptual node presents the new technologies as invaders of the scenarios that traditionally occupied the school and the educational system as transmitters of culture; Questions are raised about changes in teaching and the role of the school as a center of knowledge. For these critical analyzes of the media, the researchers present relational categories, such as pedagogical models and communicative models, pedagogical practices and communicative practices, with an epistemological approach from the pedagogical perspective.

Second node: Inclusion in education with the use of technology and the implementation of virtual education

As a result of the analysis of the reviewed articles, a second conceptual node was found that articulates the fields of special education and virtual education. There, the investigations addressed the use of technology in educational inclusion processes, both for subjects with special educational needs –with the use of support technologies– and for vulnerable populations in geographically isolated areas –with digital inclusion in virtual education.

Augmentative communication for inclusion in education

Augmentative communication as an articulating concept presents technology as a support to promote inclusion processes in education. (Paris et al., 2021) in their analysis on special education and new technologies, point out that the use of the latter allows to fulfill the "purpose of integrating subjects with special needs into the daily dynamics of every human being" (p. 3). In this discussion appears the notion of computing understood as:

...particularized expression of technology, and closely associated with information and communication, [which] materializes in programs that come in different types –simulators and microworlds– [and] allows the subject with disabilities to get closer to places, phenomena and experiences that it would hardly be possible without these resources. (p. 8).

Digital inclusion in virtual education

Digital inclusion is another articulating concept of notions related to the field of education and technology. As an element of the field of virtual education, this form of inclusion is linked to the relational category of e-learning. In this sense, (Ohlemann et al., 2023) analyze the encounter between the tradition and the competence of the school reform applied in the teacher training processes in e-learning, and point out that when these programs are designed in collaboration with the Ministry of National Education they do not achieve gain legitimacy, they also highlight the tension created in teacher training processes between the pedagogical logic of knowledge of cognition processes in learning and the technological logic that supports e-learning (Wihlenda et al., 2023).

Finally, two articles draw attention to the pedagogical aspect of virtual education. (Skandalakis et al., 2022) analyzes virtual education, questioning its pedagogical component based on three elements: virtual learning environments; the platforms; and the actors and the cultural perspective of virtual education; while (Chataika, 2023) presents digital inclusion and inclusive education as strategies to achieve social inclusion and provides concrete elements on the design of educational projects with digital inclusion.

Third node: subjectivity and the experience of interaction in technological environments

Discussions about the relationship between technology and education have changed focus in recent years. In particular, they focused on the perception of time and space, and how it affects the lives of the subjects. The experience becomes the scope and scenario of social interactions, where the subject acts and builds the interpretive systems and their symbolic universe. Education is then understood as a communicative and symbolic action, as an experience that offers subjects a political and civic education that allows their humanization and the repositioning of technology as cultural mediation (see table 3).

Subjectivity and experience

In the field of education and technology, subjectivity gained centrality as an articulating concept. as evidenced in the articles of (Pham et al., 2022), (Martín-Gómez et al., 2022) and (Thaker & Cook, 2021). The transformations in culture due to the effect of technology, both because it goes through all the interactions, and because it became the scenario for visibility and claims of different population groups, is the object of analysis of articles such as that of Levy (2000), who points out that technology has been incorporated into the dynamics of consumption and has generated a new relationship with knowledge as know-how, which is rapidly renewed. In this sense, he points out that society has appropriated the values of the capitalist economy and instrumental rationality through the use of technologies, where subjectivity runs the risk of focusing on consumption.

The first conceptual node of education and technology focused on the visibility of the role of communication and its possibilities of producing changes in the school, as evidenced in the description made by the authors, due to the entry of new technologies in the educational system and the effect of the mass media in the school. In the search for understanding and analysis of the effects of technology in education, researchers present relational categories, such as pedagogical models and communicative models, pedagogical practices and communicative practices. In addition, it is important to recognize the effort they made to generate spaces for pedagogical debate on the analysis of communication practices, the use of the media and their effects on culture, school and the educational system.

Finally, in this last node, the centrality in the field of education and technology of the relationship between subjectivity and technology as a cultural environment was perceived. By focusing on subjectivity, the role of intrasubjective and intersubjective processes, experience, interactions, the aesthetic dimension of expression and the need for political and citizenship training is recognized, to enhance subjective deployment, through educational scenarios and technology where it is built on the social experience and therefore our symbolic universe. For this purpose, the relationship of the central categories has changed; from the new fields they have been conceived in a different way, since education is recognized in its symbolic action, at the same time, educational and technological; For its part, technology is conceived as cultural mediation, cultural environment and social action.

References

- Bremner, N., Sakata, N., & Cameron, L. (2023). Teacher education as an enabler or constraint of learner-centred pedagogy implementation in low-to middle-income countries. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 126, 104033. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2023.104033>
- Carbonell-Alcocer, A., Romero-Luis, J., Gertrudix, M., & Wuebben, D. (2023). Datasets on the assessment of the scientific publication's corpora in circular economy and bioenergy approached from education and communication. *Data in Brief*, 47, 108958. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2023.108958>
- Hellin, P., Escarnot, E., Mingeot, D., Gofflot, S., Sinnaeve, G., Lateur, M., & Godin, B. (2023). Multiyear evaluation of the agronomical and technological properties of a panel of spelt varieties under different cropping environments. *Journal of Cereal Science*, 109, 103615. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcs.2022.103615>
- Hurajova, A., Kollarova, D., & Huraj, L. (2022). Trends in education during the pandemic: modern online technologies as a tool for the sustainability of university education in the field of media and communication studies. *Heliyon*, 8(5), e09367. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e09367>
- Joy, P., & Marie McSweeney-Flaherty, J. (2022). Moving Dietetics Forward with Queer Pedagogy: A Post-Structural Qualitative Study Exploring the Education and Training Experiences of Canadian Dietitians for LGBTQ Care. *Journal of the Academy of Nutrition and Dietetics*, 122(10), 1876–1884. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jand.2022.02.011>
- Klockner, K., Shields, P., Pillay, M., & Ames, K. (2021). Pragmatism as a teaching philosophy in the safety sciences: A higher education pedagogy perspective. *Safety Science*, 138, 105095. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2020.105095>
- Lopez, M., Arriaga, J. G. C., Nigenda Álvarez, J. P., González, R. T., Elizondo-Leal, J. A., Valdez-García, J. E., & Carrión, B. (2021). Virtual reality vs traditional education: Is there any advantage in human neuroanatomy teaching? *Computers & Electrical Engineering*, 93, 107282. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compeleceng.2021.107282>
- Ohlemann, S., Imhof, M., & Bellhäuser, H. (2023). Implementing reform in the teacher education system: Concerns of teacher educators. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 126, 104087. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2023.104087>
- Sabates, R., Carter, E., & Stern, J. M. B. (2021). Using educational transitions to estimate learning loss due to COVID-19 school closures: The case of Complementary Basic Education in Ghana. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 82, 102377. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedudev.2021.102377>
- Schweisfurth, M. (2023). Disaster didacticism: Pedagogical interventions and the 'learning crisis.' *International Journal of Educational Development*, 96, 102707. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedudev.2022.102707>
- Skandalakis, G. P., Chytas, D., Paraskevas, G., Noussios, G., Salmas, M., & Fiska, A. (2022). Virtual and augmented reality in anatomy education: Need for comparison with other three-dimensional visualization methods. *Morphologie*, 106(353), 141–142. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.morpho.2021.02.006>
- Wieduwilt, N., Lehl, S., & Anders, Y. (2021). Preschool teachers' pedagogical beliefs in the field of language education. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 101, 103296. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2021.103296>
- Wihlenda, M., Brahm, T., & Habisch, A. (2023). Responsible management education: Social entrepreneurial competences of civically-engaged students. *The International Journal of Management Education*, 21(1), 100756. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2022.100756>
- Xu, W. (2023). No Title. *English for Specific Purposes*, 70, 148–150. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esp.2022.12.003>
- Zhang, J., van Gorp, D., Ebberts, H., Zhou, C., & Kievit, H. (2022). Organizational legitimacy of emerging multinational enterprises: An individual perspective. *International Business Review*, 31(6), 102015. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibusrev.2022.102015>
- Zhurakovskaya, V., Sichinava, A., Simakova, T., Olicheva, O., Rykov, S., Valeeva, J., Kulachinskaya, A., & Ilyashenko, S. (2020). Innovations in Education—The Development of a New Pedagogical Technology of a Combinational Type, Focused on the Development of Personality of Students. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 6(4), 123. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.3390/joitmc6040123>